

DETERMINATION OF THE OPTIMAL INJECTION VELOCITY IN RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING BY INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

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1 Introduction

The quality and the mechanical properties of composite parts are strongly affected by the void content [1, 2]. In Resin Transfer Molding (RTM), most of the voids are formed during mold filling and result mainly of the dual porosity scale of the engineering textiles used as fibrous reinforcements.[3, 4]. Several post injection methods exist to reduce void content, such as bleeding or applying a consolidation pressure. However, most of these methods are expensive and cannot be easily implemented to parts of complex geometry or very large pieces.

Macroscopic voids are formed between the fiber tows when the velocity is too low (flow driven by capillary forces), whereas microscopic voids appear inside fiber tows when the velocity is too high (flow driven by viscous forces). It was proven that an intermediate optimal injection velocity range exists that minimizes void formation during resin injection [5, 6]. This velocity range is specific of each combination of resin and fabric. As shown in Fig. 1, the void content in composite samples describes a “V-shaped” curve as a function of the injection velocity. The optimal velocity range can be determined by capillary rise experiments at low impregnation velocity.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Capillary rise experiments

The capillary rise experiment is a well-known method to characterize the impregnation of materials by capillary flows. It is used in different fields such as textiles, porous media, soils, etc. The principle of

this technique consists of dipping the sample material in a recipient containing the infiltration fluid and measure the evolution of the impregnation in time.

The classical measurements record the mass of the absorbed fluid and/or the height of the capillary front. The mass of the absorbed fluid is an effective way to quantify the impregnation, but it is difficult to connect this measurement with the velocity of the infiltration fluid, because the level of saturation of the porous medium is unknown and varies in time. Different visible techniques exist to measure the height of the fluid front. It consists of recording images during the capillary rise and determining the positions of the capillary front by image processing. A powerful method using a fluorescent dye has been developed for glass fibers reinforcement (see Fig. 2)[7, 8].

However, these capillary rise experiments are based upon the optical visualization of the resin flow front. Therefore it is not possible to extend these techniques to non-transparent reinforcements such as carbon fibers. Since these latter types of fibrous reinforcements are widely used, it is primordial to estimate the optimal injection velocity in this case. This is why the experimental procedure needs to be modified in order to characterize carbon fiber reinforcements by capillary rise experiments.

2.2 Infrared thermography applied to capillary rise measurements

InfraRed Thermography (IRT) has become a widely used measurement technique in research and engineering, especially in the Non Destructive Testing (NDT) of composites [9]. Infrared thermography (IRT) has already been used for

capillary rise measurements, but only as a visualization tool [10]. Indeed, it enabled to locate the flow front in porous media samples and plot the evolution of the fluid height in time during the capillary rise. This investigation aims to study the possibility of using IRT as a quantitative technique to follow the evolution of the capillary front in time during the imbibition of carbon fiber engineering textiles.

The experimental setup is inspired from the initial work carried out in transparent fibers with a fluorescent liquid and ultraviolet image acquisition. Fig. 2 shows a diagram of the initial setup [11], but in the IRT technique the balance, the UV light source and the HD camera are no longer necessary.

In this new approach, the main experimental difficulty is connected with the thermal signal required to visualize the evolution of the capillary front. If the reinforcement and the fluid are both at room temperature, no temperature changes occur during imbibition. Therefore a thermal contrast needs to be created between the liquid and the fibrous reinforcement in order to visualize the temperature changes resulting from liquid infiltration. Several approaches will be considered either by increasing or decreasing the fluid or the reinforcement temperature.

Different tests have been carried out and the retained option was to slightly increase the fluid temperature via a temperature controller and a heated plate (see Fig. 3). Indeed, it is not possible to control precisely the sample temperature, since it is subjected to convection and heat transfer, whereas the fluid temperature is more stable and easier to control. The whole experimental setup is installed in an insulated dark room in order to avoid air motions, vibrations, external light, as well as to minimize heat transfer.

Samples of 1" x 3" were prepared with 2D glass fibrous reinforcements from JB Martin TG15N and with 2D carbon fibers from Sigmatec SC622. The liquid used for the experiments is hexadecane, which is a perfectly wetting fluid of well-known physical properties (density, viscosity, contact angle). In this configuration, IR images were recorded during the capillary rise at different frame rates (1 and 5 Hz, i.e., 1 and 5 frames per second). Every image is a 2D matrix giving the temperature field in Celsius degrees. No image compression is applied such as in jpeg files. This allows a better accuracy for further post-processing.

An example of 2D temperature field extracted from a capillary rise experiment is shown in Fig. 4. The whole sequence of temperature fields is a set of 2D matrices, which can be considered as a 3D matrix with time as third dimension. This sequence of images is imported into Matlab software for post-processing. An inverse technique is then used to estimate the velocity from the temperature fields. The next section describes the algorithm used for that purpose.

3 Numerical method

3.1 Thermal modelization

Inverse techniques are well known in heat transfer problems, and very useful in the case of infrared thermography [12]. In order to retrieve the velocity of the fluid from the temperature field, a thermal model needs to be introduced. In the case of capillary rise experiments in a two dimensional fabric, the physical phenomenon can be considered as bidimensional, because the thickness is negligible compared to the length and width of the samples. The heat equation can be written in the fibrous reinforcement, as follows:

$$\rho_{rf} C_{p_{rf}} \frac{\partial T_{rf}}{\partial t} = \lambda_{rf} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_{rf}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_{rf}}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density (kg.m^{-3}), C_p the heat capacity ($\text{kJ.kg}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$), T the temperature ($^{\circ}\text{K}$), t the time (s), λ , the thermal conductivity ($\text{W.m}^{-1}.\text{K}^{-1}$) and x , y represent the space coordinates (m). The subscript rf stand for the fibrous reinforcement.

In the infiltration fluid, the heat equation becomes:

$$\rho_{fl} C_{p_{fl}} \frac{\partial T_{fl}}{\partial t} + \rho_{fl} C_{p_{fl}} v_y \frac{\partial T_{fl}}{\partial y} = \lambda_{fl} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_{fl}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T_{fl}}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where v_y is the velocity in the y direction (m.s^{-1}) and the subscript fl stands for the liquid.

The fluid flow during the capillary rise is mainly vertical (i.e., in the y direction), thus the velocity in the x direction can be neglected. During the capillary rise, three different temperatures can be

distinguished: the fluid temperature T_{fl} , the reinforcement temperature T_{rf} , and the observed temperature T_{obs} via the camera. Given the geometry and the high thermal conductivity of the reinforcement sample, there is a short time lapse at the beginning of the capillary rise when the fluid and the reinforcement temperatures are equal:

$$T_{obs} = T_{rf} = T_{fl} = T \quad (3)$$

During this time lapse, the thermal front visualized with the camera corresponds to the fluid front inside the reinforcement. After this time lapse, the thermal front is blurry and does not correspond to the fluid front anymore. This is due to convective heat transfer around the sample (see Fig. 5). This means that the estimation of the velocity will be possible only at the beginning of the capillary rise, when the liquid and thermal fronts are superimposed.

This time constraint does not represent a major problem, because we are interested in the estimation of the spontaneous imbibition velocity, namely at the onset of impregnation.

Moreover, the IR camera allows recording images at a high frequency, hence increasing the amount of data available during this short time lapse at the beginning of the capillary rise experiment.

Thus, the hypothesis stated in the equation (3) is valid, and it is possible to combine the equations (1) and (2) in order to rewrite the thermal model as follows:

$$\rho_M C_{p_M} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho_{fl} C_{p_{fl}} v_Y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \lambda_M \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (4)$$

3.2 Inverse technique algorithm

The IR camera records images on a regular grid with square pixels, thus the spatial steps in the x and y directions are equal so that

$$\Delta x = \Delta y \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, the time step Δt between two consecutive images is known from the camera.

Therefore, it is possible to discretize equation (4) by finite difference to obtain the following equation:

$$\rho_M C_{p_M} \frac{T_{i,j}^{k+1} - T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta t} + \rho_{hex} C_{p_{hex}} v_{Yi,j} \frac{T_{i,j+1}^k - T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta y} = \lambda_M \frac{T_{i,j+1}^k + T_{i,j-1}^k + T_{i+1,j}^k + T_{i-1,j}^k - 4T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta y^2} \quad (6)$$

where M denotes properties of the composite, i.e., the liquid the mixed thermo-physical properties are evaluated by the rule of mixture as expressed in the following equations :

$$\rho_M C_{p_M} = \rho_{hex} C_{p_{hex}} \phi + \rho_{ref} C_{p_{ref}} (1 - \phi) \quad (7)$$

$$\lambda_M = \lambda_{hex} \phi + \lambda_{ref} (1 - \phi) \quad (8)$$

where ϕ (%) denotes the porosity of the reinforcement.

Assuming that all the thermo physical properties are known (see table 1), the only unknown in equation (6) is the velocity v_Y of the capillary front which will be estimated from the IR images. Equation (6) can be rewritten in the following simplified form:

$$C1_{i,j} + v_{Yi,j} C2_{i,j} = C3_{i,j} \quad (9)$$

where $C1$, $C2$ and $C3$ are respectively proportional to the time and spatial derivatives, and the Laplacian of the temperature fields, as defined below:

$$C1_{i,j} = \rho_M C_{p_M} \frac{T_{i,j}^{k+1} - T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta t} \quad (10)$$

$$C2_{i,j} = \rho_{hex} C_{p_{hex}} \frac{T_{i,j+1}^k - T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta y} \quad (11)$$

$$C3_{i,j} = \lambda_M \frac{T_{i,j+1}^k + T_{i,j-1}^k + T_{i+1,j}^k + T_{i-1,j}^k - 4T_{i,j}^k}{\Delta y^2} \quad (12)$$

It is then possible to estimate the velocity from the temperature fields, as follows:

$$v_{Yi,j} = \frac{C3_{i,j} - C1_{i,j}}{C2_{i,j}} \quad (13)$$

Thus, a value of the velocity can be calculated for every pixel (i,j) of the thermal image, allowing to directly generate a map of the estimated velocity field without having to detect the liquid height at several intermediate steps.

3.3 Capillary number and resin velocity determination

The velocity values from the inverse technique are suitable for hexadecane and glass fibers. It is possible to calculate the equivalent velocity for resins without carrying out capillary tests with resins. Indeed, the modified capillary number Ca^* is defined as in equation (14) from the velocity [13, 14]:

$$Ca^* = \frac{\mu_{hex} \cdot v_{hex}}{\gamma_{hex} \cos \theta_{hex}} \quad (14)$$

The modified capillary number takes into account the contact angle, thus it remains constant for other liquids using the same fabrics in the same operating conditions. Therefore the optimal injection velocity of the resin v_{resin} can be calculated by equation (15):

$$v_{resin} = Ca^* \cdot \frac{\gamma_{resin} \cos \theta_{resin}}{\mu_{resin}} \quad (15)$$

The optimal injection velocity is evaluated for two typical resins used with the JB Martin fabric: the Derakane 411-350 vinyl ester and the DER 383 epoxy resins. The viscosity of these resins was measured as a function of the temperature with an Anton-Paar MCR-501 rheometer. The surface tensions were extrapolated from measurements at 20°C and 50°C [15]. The contact angle measured at room temperature by optical means with a Ramé-Hart NRL-100 goniometer is assumed to remain constant in temperature.

4 Results

4.1 Glass fiber reinforcements

The reinforcement samples of JB Martin TG15N NCF were cut along the warp direction. The fluid was first heated to 30°C. The thermal images are cropped according to the region of interest shown in Fig. 4 before being processed. As shown in Fig. 6, the thermal and fluid fronts are superimposed at the

beginning of the capillary rise, but rapidly, the thermal front is stopped because a state of thermal equilibrium is established with the surrounding air.

From these temperature fields, the inverse technique algorithm gives the velocity field shown in Fig. 7. On the first image ($t = 4.119$ s), the fluid is not rising yet; so no velocity can be estimated. On the second image ($t = 4.306$ s), the fluid starts to rise; thus local temperature variations can be estimated. On the next images ($t = 4.54$ s and $t = 4.77$ s), the velocity is estimated only where the temperature varies. Indeed, since the temperature does not change on the pixels where the fluid has already been detected, the estimation needs not to be performed again on those pixels.

As shown in Fig. 8, it is possible to represent a cumulative velocity map), on which the “fingering effect” can be observed, i.e., the faster velocity front inside the fiber tows.

Fig. 9 shows the mean velocity value calculated on each frame and plotted against time. It is clear that the method is repeatable and works efficiently for the first frames of the capillary rise. But when the thermal signal becomes too low (after $t > 5$ s for example), the value of the estimated velocity tends to zero, which is not representative of the physical phenomenon.

Given the large amount of data available (one pixel = one value of velocity), the mean values plotted in Fig. 9 are relevant. The spontaneous optimal velocity corresponds to the peak of the velocity curves displayed in Fig. 9.

The experiments were repeated at different temperatures and for several acquisition frequencies (see Fig. 10). For both acquisition frequencies tested, the estimated velocity increases with temperature. However, the results at 1 Hz are less stable and the standard deviation becomes larger. Increasing the frame rate to 5 Hz yielded a better accuracy and more stable results. Indeed, with only 1 frame per second, a part of the signal can be averaged and biased between two frames. This can generate an error especially between the two first frames (right after the contact of the fabric with the fluid). Thus, it was concluded that all future analyses should be carried out at a frequency of 5 Hz.

The equivalent resin velocity is calculated by equations (14) and (15). The results are presented in Table 2. At 30°C they compare well to those obtained in [15] by the visible imaging technique at

room temperature (22.5 ± 2 °C). This proves the efficiency of this new approach and validates the experimental procedure based on infrared thermography (IRT). This protocol can now be applied to non-transparent carbon fabrics.

4.2 Carbon fiber reinforcements

Samples of Sigmalex SC622 carbon fabrics were cut in the warp direction. As reported in the validation tests with glass fibers samples in the previous section, the capillary rise tests were performed at 30°C, 40°C and 50°C with a recording frequency of 5 Hz. The same image treatment and estimation procedure is applied to the carbon fiber reinforcements. Samples images from the capillary rise tests on carbon fibers at 30°C are shown in Fig. 11. Carbon is more conductive than glass, therefore the thermal images are more subject to noise and the thermal front is harder to locate. Therefore it is difficult to measure the liquid height like in the classical optical methods. However, in the new approach proposed in this investigation, the blurry effect of the fluid and thermal fronts is not a limitation because the IR estimation method based on finite differences allows a direct estimation and mapping of the velocity field..

The instantaneous estimated velocity maps are shown in Fig. 12. As already observed for glass fiber reinforcements, the velocity can only be estimated where a temperature difference occurs between two images. Note that a cumulative velocity map can also be drawn as shown in Fig. 13. Since the geometrical properties and the weaving/stitching structure is different for the carbon fabric tested, no “fingering” effect is observed. This means that the flow behavior is different.

The mean value of velocity is calculated on each frame and plotted in time (as shown in Fig. 14). Since the noise is greater for carbon fibers, the estimation technique cannot generate results when the thermal signal is too low, and no values were returned. This is why there are apparently less points in Fig. 14 than in Fig. 9. However, the returned values of Fig. 14 are reliable and correspond to the spontaneous imbibition velocity.

The experiments were repeated at different temperatures. The spontaneous imbibition velocity is plotted as a function of temperature in Fig. 15. The same trend is observed as in glass fiber

reinforcements: the velocity tends to increase with temperature.

The same order of magnitude is observed for of the estimated velocity in carbon and in glass fabrics. But the estimated velocities in the carbon fabrics are slightly higher compared to the glass fabrics. This is due to the architecture of the carbon fabrics, which have a smaller hydraulic diameter, and thus exhibit a greater capillary pressure. Note that the velocity could be affected by the value of thermal conductivity of carbon used in the algorithm. This parameter should be studied and measured accurately in order to refine the results. The equivalent velocity for the epoxy and vinyl ester resins considered could not be calculated since the contact angle of such fluids with carbon is not known.

5 Conclusion

In this study, a new experimental protocol and numerical method were proposed in order to estimate the optimal injection velocity of resins through 2D fabrics for RTM processes. The new method is based on the improvement of capillary rise measurements. Since carbon fibers are completely opaque to light, the classical optical techniques are no longer relevant. For this reason the InfraRed Thermography (IRT) was implemented and validated in this investigation by comparing the IRT results with a classical optical method. The optimal velocity through 2D glass fiber fabrics was in good agreement for the two resins considered (vinyl ester and epoxy). The method also permitted to estimate the optimal velocity as a function of temperature.

The experimental results for 2D carbon fiber fabrics gave also the optimal velocity as a function of the temperature. Since no previous results are available for carbon fibers, the results would still need to be validated by injections void content analysis of carbon based composites and.

Although some parameters such as thermal conductivity and emissivity or the thermal model can still be adjusted to improve the estimation, the first results obtained are promising. One of the main advantages of the proposed new method lies in the optimal velocity maps generated, that increase considerably the number of data and hence reduce the estimation error. Note that this study was limited to single plies at temperatures between 30°C and

50°C. In order to apply this approach to aerospace materials, the next step would consist of studying 3D carbon fabrics at higher temperatures.

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Fig. 3: New experimental setup for capillary rise measurements using infrared thermography (IRT).

Fig. 1: Theoretical percentage of voids as a function of the injection velocity in composites parts.

Fig. 4: Example of a 2D temperature field (IR image) during a capillary rise experiment with hexadecane and a glass fibers reinforcement.

Fig. 2: Initial experimental setup for capillary rise visible measurements.

Fig. 5: Visualization of the fluid and thermal fronts for (a) short times and (b) after a long time of capillary rise experiment.

Fig. 7: Instantaneous estimated velocity fields from temperature fields during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers reinforcements.

Fig. 6: Temperature fields during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers reinforcements, recorded at 5Hz.

Fig. 8: Cumulative velocity field from instantaneous estimations during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers reinforcements.

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Fig. 9: Mean value of the estimated velocity as a function of time during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers reinforcements.

Fig. 10: Evolution of the estimated optimal velocity as a function of the temperature during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers fabrics. Influence of the recording frequency.

Fig. 11: Temperature fields during capillary rise of hexadecane through carbon fibers reinforcements, recorded at 5Hz.

Fig. 12: Instantaneous estimated velocity fields from temperature fields during capillary rise of hexadecane through carbon fibers reinforcements.

Fig. 13: Cumulative velocity field from instantaneous estimations during capillary rise of hexadecane through carbon fibers reinforcements

Fig. 14: Mean value of the estimated velocity as a function of time during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers reinforcements.

Fig. 15: Evolution of the estimated optimal velocity as a function of the temperature during capillary rise of hexadecane through glass fibers fabrics.

Table 1: Thermo physical properties used for the reinforcements samples and the fluid.

	ρ (kg.m-3)	C_p (kJ.kg ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	λ (W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)
Glass fibers	2500	720	1
Carbon fibers	1800	700	100
Hexadecane	770	7200	0.15 [16]

Table 2: Estimated optimal injection velocities for two resins through JB Martin TG15N glass fibers fabrics. (N.D = Non Determined).

T(°C)	v_y Vinyl ester (mm.s ⁻¹)		v_y Epoxy (mm.s ⁻¹)	
	this work	Lebel [15]	this work	Lebel [15]
30	0,149	0,18	0,138	0,14
40	0,255	N.D	0,267	N.D
50	0,433	N.D	0,508	N.D